

UKBOL Standard Operating Procedure: Submitting specimen images to BOLD systems v.5

Version 1, March 2026

Contents

Filling Image Metadata Sheet.....	2
Compressing images.....	9
Submitting to BOLD.....	12

1. Start by opening up the relevant BOLD processing sheet.

2. And make sure that the sheet is labelled as 'bold', by right clicking on the tab that says 'Sheet1' and clicking on Rename.

3. Click on the + sign to add another tab, and rename this tab 'target'.

5	UK001-D01	NHМУK010887632	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
6	UK001-E01	NHМУK010887633	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
7	UK001-F01	NHМУK010887634	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
8	UK001-G01	NHМУK010887635	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
9	UK001-H01	NHМУK010887636	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
10	UK001-A02	NHМУK010887637	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
11	UK001-B02	NHМУK010887638	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
12	UK001-C02	NHМУK010887639	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
13	UK001-D02	NHМУK010887640	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
14	UK001-E02	NHМУK010887641	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
15	UK001-F02	NHМУK010887642	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
16	UK001-G02	NHМУK010887643	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
17	UK001-H02	NHМУK010887644	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi
18	UK001-A03	NHМУK010887645	NHМУK	Natural Hi: Defra, Nat Arthi

Navigation bar: < > bold +

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1											
2											
3											
4											
5											
6											
7											
8											
9											
10											
11											
12											
13											
14											
15											
16											
17											
18											

Navigation bar: < > bold target +

4. Go to the folder containing all of the images that you want to submit to BOLD.
5. Start by selecting all of the images by clicking on one and typing **ctrl + A**.

6. **Right click** on the selected images and click on 'Copy as path' OR type **ctrl + shift + C**.

- Paste it into column A in 'target' and then click on 'Automate' in the tool bar and run the script below OR click on New Script and copy and paste the code if not done already:

- IF you don't have the script already;** after clicking on 'New Script', highlight all of the code already there (it's a template Excel gives you) and delete it.

9. Copy the code from this github link and paste it into the script text box (there is a README.md file also available for more information):

[UKBOL_NHMUK/SOP_submitting_images_to_BOLD/UKBOL_populating_image_template_script.ts](#) at main · sophrein/UKBOL_NHMUK

10. After running this script your 'target' sheet should look like this:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	NHMUK013587062	dorsal	013587062_dorsal.jpg	UK007-E01				
2	NHMUK013587062	lateral	013587062_lateral.jpg	UK007-E01				
3	NHMUK013587088	dorsal	013587088_dorsal.jpg	UK007-F01				
4	NHMUK013587088	lateral	013587088_lateral.jpg	UK007-F01				
5	NHMUK014015102	dorsal	014015102_dorsal.jpg	UK007-G01				
6	NHMUK014015102	lateral	014015102_lateral.jpg	UK007-G01				
7	NHMUK014015114	dorsal	014015114_dorsal.jpg	UK007-H01				
8	NHMUK014015114	lateral	014015114_lateral.jpg	UK007-H01				
9	NHMUK014015117	dorsal	014015117_dorsal.jpg	UK007-C02				
10	NHMUK014015117	lateral	014015117_lateral.jpg	UK007-C02				
11	NHMUK014015127	dorsal	014015127_dorsal.jpg	UK007-D02				
12	NHMUK014015127	lateral	014015127_lateral.jpg	UK007-D02				
13	NHMUK014015141	dorsal	014015141_dorsal.jpg	UK007-E02				
14	NHMUK014015141	lateral	014015141_lateral.jpg	UK007-E02				
15	NHMUK016605199	dorsal	016605199_dorsal.jpg	UK007-B10				
16	NHMUK016605200	dorsal	016605200_dorsal.jpg	UK007-C10				
17	NHMUK016605201	dorsal	016605201_dorsal.jpg	UK007-D10				
18	NHMUK016605202	dorsal	016605202_dorsal.jpg	UK007-E10				

11. Open [ImageData.xlsx](#) the downloadable BOLD image metadata template (copy it to a new excel sheet if the template is shared across a team), and fill these columns with the data you have above.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
	Image File	Original Specimen	View Metadata	Caption	Measurement	Measurement Type	Sample Id	Process Id	License Holder
1	013587062_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-E01		
2	013587062_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-E01		
3	013587088_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-F01		
4	013587088_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-F01		
5	014015102_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-G01		
6	014015102_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-G01		
7	014015114_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-H01		
8	014015114_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-H01		
9	014015117_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-C02		
10	014015117_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-C02		
11	014015127_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-D02		
12	014015127_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-D02		
13	014015141_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-E02		
14	014015141_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-E02		
15	016605199_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-B10		
16	016605200_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-C10		
17	016605201_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-D10		
18	016605202_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-E10		
19	016605203_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-F10		
20	016605204_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-G10		
21	016605205_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-H10		
22	016605206_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-A11		
23	016605207_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-B11		
24	016605208_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-C11		
25	016605209_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-D11		
26	016605210_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-E11		
27	016605211_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-F11		
28	016605212_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-G11		
29	016605213_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-H11		
30	016605214_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-A12		
31	016605215_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-B12		

Column D copy from target to **Column G** in template

Column B copy from target to **Column C** in template

Column C copy from target to **Column A** in template

(ignore the NHMUK barcodes, they do not need to go into the image data spreadsheet)

12. Write 'yes' into column B of the template and drag down the green square at the right bottom corner to copy it down the rest of the rows.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
	Image File	Original Specimen	View Metadata	Caption	Measurement	Measurement Type	Sample Id	Process Id	License Holder	License	License Year
2	013587062_dorsal.jpg	yes	dorsal				UK007-E01				
3	013587062_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-E01				
4	013587088_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-F01				
5	013587088_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-F01				
6	014015102_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-G01				
7	014015102_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-G01				
8	014015114_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-H01				
9	014015114_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-H01				
10	014015117_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-C02				
11	014015117_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-C02				
12	014015127_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-D02				
13	014015127_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-D02				
14	014015141_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-E02				
15	014015141_lateral.jpg		lateral				UK007-E02				
16	016605199_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-B10				
17	016605200_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-C10				
18	016605201_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-D10				
19	016605202_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-E10				
20	016605203_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-F10				
21	016605204_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-G10				
22	016605205_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-H10				
23	016605206_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-A11				
24	016605207_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-B11				
25	016605208_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-C11				
26	016605209_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-D11				
27	016605210_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-E11				
28	016605211_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-F11				
29	016605212_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-G11				
30	016605213_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-H11				
31	016605214_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-A12				
32	016605215_dorsal.jpg		dorsal				UK007-B12				

13. Copy in License and Photographer metadata into the template.

- 'The Trustees of the Natural History Museum, London' into Column I ('License Holder')
- 'CreativeCommons Attribution (by)' into Column J ('License')
- 'Natural History Museum, London' into Column L ('License Institution')
- Write name of photographer into column N ('Photographer')

16. Now open up the XNConvert application, go onto Actions > click on Add action > Transform > Resize.

17. Go onto the Custom scroll down menu and choose '50%'.

18. Your action settings should look like this:

19. Make sure that in Filename it just says {Filename}, and that you set the folder path to where you want to save all the compressed images, then press convert.

20. All of the compressed images and metadata spreadsheet should be saved into the folder of your choice.
21. Make sure all the images along with the ImageData.xls file created earlier are together in a folder, select everything, click on the three dots and compress to a .zip file.

22. Now log into your BOLD account and click on 'projects' dropdown on the left panel and then 'View All Projects'.

Projects

Specimens

Uploads

Sequences Traces Images

Primers Publication Checklist

Your Datasets: 0

Recently Accessed

Code	Title	Specimens	Accessed
UKAN	UK Barcoding - Animals COI-5P[2207]	6741	today
DEFRA	UKBOL accelerated COI-5P[0], ITS2[0], rbcL[0], matK[0], ITS[0], ITS1[0]	0	today
GENPR	Private holding project for various ongoing studies	162	2 days ago

23. Once you are in 'My Projects' click on 'DEFRA'.

My Projects

General Projects 15 Projects, 20158 Specimens

Code	Title	Public	Specimens	Species	Species with Sequences Markers [stats]	Sequences Markers [stats]	Project Tags
<input type="checkbox"/> GENPR	Private holding project for various ongoing studies		162	36	COI-5P[0]	COI-5P[0]	
<input type="checkbox"/> UKBOL	UK Barcoding	↔	25194	5853	COI-5P[2433], ITS2[1116], rbcL[1445], matK[1345], ITS[0], ITS1[0]	COI-5P[7399], ITS2[2588], rbcL[4516], matK[3263], ITS[0], ITS1[0]	
<input type="checkbox"/> ANBIO	Ainsdale BioBlitz	↔	625	311	COI-5P[244]	COI-5P[479]	
<input type="checkbox"/> ASCEN	Expanding genetic biomonitoring on Ascension Island	↔	0	0	COI-5P[0], ITS[0]	COI-5P[0], ITS[0]	
<input type="checkbox"/> BURE	Bure Marshes Bioblitz	↔	378	281	COI-5P[142]	COI-5P[159]	
<input type="checkbox"/> DEFRA	UKBOL accelerated	↔	0	0	COI-5P[0], ITS2[0], rbcL[0], matK[0], ITS[0], ITS1[0]	COI-5P[0], ITS2[0], rbcL[0], matK[0], ITS[0], ITS1[0]	
<input type="checkbox"/> FBUK	FreshBase: UK freshwater macroinvertebrate genomic reference collection	↔	490	428	COI-5P[213]	COI-5P[254]	
<input type="checkbox"/> HELEN	St Helena Barcode Reference Library	↔	81	65	COI-5P[45]	COI-5P[57]	h Merge
<input type="checkbox"/> MISSM	Mission Malaise	↔	8550	0	COI-5P[0]	COI-5P[3336]	

24. And then click on the 'Uploads' dropdown on the left panel and click on 'Specimen Images'.

The Image submission window will pop up.

25. Click on 'Choose File' and upload the .zip file.

26. Fill the description with your '[batch number] – images' and any other relevant information and then click submit.

